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SHORT COMMUNICATION

The Truth about mRNA Vaccines

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INTRODUCTION

- All RNA viruses, by entering the host cell, secure their own reproduction because its RNA is attached to the enzyme "RT - reverse transcriptase" to form an immediate "DNA library" that will be incorporated into the genome of the host cell by another enzyme - the "integrase".
- If this were not the case, viral infections caused by RNA viruses would not be possible, as the "proteases", in other words the scavenger cells, would destroy the viral RNA.
- The same applies to RNA or mRNA fragments to avoid the action of proteases.
- In addition, even if an RNA or mRNA fragment protected by some kind of encapsulation were to be introduced, it would never trigger ribosome activity to produce the SPIKE that, once expelled from the cell, is key to the immune response, because two preconditions are vital for activating the ribosomes:
 1. A change in the "oxidation-reduction" state (REDOX state). The oxide/reductive state plays a fundamental role within the cell. It is to the cell what the pH is to the blood. The value of the oxide/reductive state conditions and establishes the activities of the cell.
 2. Activation of "Nucleus Factors", the only ones that can spur the genome to initiate protein Synthesis.

Points 1 and 2 outline what happens every time a virus enters a cell because it alters its REDOX state, which then activates the 'Nucleus Factors'.

Never do ribosomes process an mRNA, unless it comes directly from the genome.

As a consequence, in order to stop the SPIKE, mRNA vaccines must be incorporated into the cell at its genomic level.

- Thus, mRNA is a misnomer because per se it will never be able to activate ribosomes [1-5].

DISCUSSION

In the COVID-19 mRNA vaccines in use, there can only be a fragment of viral RNA relating to the SPIKE already triggered by the enzyme 'RT - Reverse Transcriptase'.

A simple experiment is all it takes to substantiate this claim:

1. Inject a COVID-19 mRNA vaccine into a cell culture
2. After a set time period has elapsed, the action of SPIKE simulating a low frequency SARS-Cov2 infection will be noticeable.

The SPIKE that is acting is a genome expression of the cells in culture.

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CONCLUSION

The manufacturers of the latest COVID-19 mRNA vaccines have been lying, alleging that the mRNA would produce the SPIKE, without integrating into the host cell genome, and ultimately destroying itself in the short term.

A worldwide pandemic cannot be stopped by scientific lies, which invalidate the fundamental principles of biology.

REFERENCES

1. Ansovini Technology Patent US8852582B2.
2. Ansovini R. Determination of an Antiviral Activity of a Composition Comprising

Glutathione Reductase (GSSG-R) and Oxidized Glutathione (GSSG) for Pharmaceutical use: Experiments In vitro and In vivo. *J Biomed Res Environ Sci.* 2020 Jun 17;1(2):029-038. doi: 10.37871/jels1117

3. Ansovini R, Compagnucci L. The Hypothetical Role of Erythrocytes in COVID-19: Immediate Clinical Therapy. *J Biomed Res Environ Sci.* 2020 Jul 02;1(3): 048-050. doi: 10.37871/jels1119
4. Ansovini R, Compagnucci L. Use of Polio Vaccine Salk vs SARS- CoV-2E and HIV-1E 2, both as Therapeutic Drug and Effective Vaccine to Make Memory-Cells Able to Stop Reinfections. *J Biomed Res Environ Sci.* 2020 Nov 18;1(7):311-312. doi: 10.37871/jbres1160
5. Doerfler W. Adenoviral Vector DNA- and SARS-CoV-2 mRNA-Based Covid-19 Vaccines: Possible Integration into the Human Genome - Are Adenoviral Genes Expressed in Vector-based Vaccines? *Virus Res.* 2021 Sep;302:198466. doi: 10.1016/j.virusres.2021.198466. Epub 2021 Jun 1. PMID: 34087261; PMCID: PMC8168329.

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